

FILM MARKET, DISTRIBUTION AND CINEMA EXHIBITION SYSTEM

Qalandarov Izzat Omonboyevich

Senior Lecturer, Department of Sound
Directing and Cinematography,
Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture
izzatqalandarov88@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19067364>

Annotation

This thesis analyzes the interrelationship between the film market, film distribution, and the cinema theater system, as well as their role in the film industry. The study examines the organizational and economic mechanisms of the exhibition process from film production to its delivery to the audience. It also highlights the distribution system of film products and the factors influencing the development of cinema theater networks based on international experience. The impact of film market infrastructure on the development of national cinema is scientifically substantiated.

Аннотация

В тезисе анализируется взаимосвязь кинорынка, кинодистрибуции и системы кинотеатров, а также их роль в киноиндустрии. Рассматриваются организационные и экономические механизмы прокатного процесса от производства фильма до его доведения до зрителя. Также на основе мирового опыта освещаются система распространения кино продукции и факторы развития сети кинотеатров. Научно обосновывается влияние инфраструктуры кинорынка на развитие национального кинематографа.

Annotatsiya

Tezisdagi kino bozori, film distribyutsiyasi va kinoteatrlar tizimining o'zaro bog'liqligi hamda ularning kino industriyasidagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Film ishlab chiqarishdan tomoshabinga yetib borishigacha bo'lgan prokat jarayonining tashkiliy va iqtisodiy mexanizmlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, jahon tajribasi asosida kino mahsulotini tarqatish tizimi va kinoteatrlar tarmog'ining rivojlanish omillari yoritiladi. Kino bozori infratuzilmasining milliy kino rivojiga ta'siri ilmiy jihatdan asoslab beriladi.

Keywords: film market, film distribution, film exhibition, cinema theater system, film industry, film distribution mechanism, audience, cinema infrastructure, digital distribution, national film market.

Ключевые слова: кинорынок, кинодистрибуция, кинопрокат, система кинотеатров, киноиндустрия, механизм распространения фильмов,

зрительская аудитория, киноинфраструктура, цифровая дистрибуция, национальный кинорынок.

Kalit so'zlar: kino bozori, film distribyutsiyasi, kino prokati, kinoteatrlar tizimi, kino industriyasi, film tarqatish mexanizmi, tomoshabin auditoriyasi, kino infratuzilmasi, raqamli distribyutsiya, milliy kino bozori

Introduction

The film industry is not only a product of artistic creativity but also a cultural field characterized by a complex economic and organizational system. Within this system, the film market, film distribution, and cinema theater networks function as key components that ensure the process from the creation of a film to its delivery to the audience. Through market mechanisms and distribution systems, film products are brought to a wide audience, while cinemas represent the final stage of this process by directly connecting the film with viewers. Therefore, the effective development of the film industry largely depends on the level of development of market infrastructure, distribution activities, and the cinema theater system.

Today, as the film industry is rapidly developing within the global media space, the issue of effectively distributing film products and delivering them to audiences has become particularly relevant. Along with the increasing volume of film production, there is a growing need to improve market mechanisms, distribution strategies, and cinema infrastructure. In particular, the emergence of digital technologies and new media platforms has fundamentally transformed the forms of film distribution and has contributed to the formation of a new model of the film market. Therefore, the scientific analysis of the film market, distribution, and cinema theater systems, as well as the study of their modern development trends, is of significant scientific and practical importance.

The purpose of this research is to scientifically analyze the interrelationship between the film market, film distribution, and the cinema theater system, as well as their functional significance within the film industry. Based on this objective, the study aims to identify the characteristics of the formation of the film market, examine the organizational mechanisms of film distribution, and highlight the role of cinema theater systems in delivering film products to audiences. Additionally, analyzing the development trends of distribution and exhibition systems in the modern film industry and determining their impact on the national film market is considered one of the important tasks of this research.

The Concept of the Film Market and Its Formation

The film market represents a complex system that integrates the economic and cultural activities of the film industry. It encompasses a set of economic relations that include film production, its distribution, and delivery to the audience. At the same time, the film market is not only a source of economic profit but also directly influences the formation of society's aesthetic taste, cultural values, and audience demand. Therefore, the film market can be considered a specific cultural and economic system closely connected with both economic interests and cultural processes.

The success of a film product in the film market largely depends on how effectively it operates within market mechanisms. These mechanisms include processes such as promoting the film after production, distributing it, and delivering it to audiences through various exhibition platforms. In the film market, film products circulate based on the principles of supply and demand, where audience preferences, marketing strategies, and exhibition policies play an important role. As a result, the economic efficiency of a film and the extent of its audience reach depend on how effectively these market mechanisms are organized.

The functioning of the film market is formed through the cooperation of various stakeholders. The main participants in this system include film producers (production companies and film studios), distributors, cinema theater networks, and the audience. In addition, government institutions, investors, and advertising and cultural marketing organizations also play an important role in the development of the film market. The interaction and cooperation of these participants form a unified system that ensures the entry of film products into the market, their distribution, and their delivery to audiences.

Film Distribution and Exhibition System

The film distribution and exhibition system includes the main stages of delivering a film product to the audience after its production. This process begins with developing a strategy for releasing the film to the market, organizing advertising and marketing campaigns, and preparing it for exhibition. At the next stage, the film is distributed through distributors to cinema theater networks, television channels, or digital platforms. As a result, the film reaches the audience through screenings and demonstrates its cultural as well as economic value.

Distribution activities perform several important functions related to promoting a film effectively in the film market and delivering it to a wide audience. First, the distributor develops the film's exhibition strategy, determines the territories and timing of its release, and establishes contractual relations with

cinema theaters. In addition, promoting the film, conducting marketing campaigns, and attracting audience attention are also important tasks of distribution activities. Thus, the distributor acts as a key link that ensures the successful presentation of a film product in the market environment and its economic efficiency.

In the modern film industry, film distribution is carried out through various exhibition platforms. Traditionally, cinema theaters were considered the main venue for film screenings; however, today television channels and digital platforms also play an important role in distributing film products. In particular, with the development of internet technologies, online streaming services have created opportunities to quickly deliver films to a wide global audience. As a result, film distribution has become a multi-platform system, elevating the forms of film exhibition and interaction with audiences to a new level.

Cinema Theater System and Audience

The network of cinema theaters is an important component of the film market and serves as the main venue where films directly meet their audiences. They occupy a central place in the exhibition process of film products and directly influence both the commercial success of films and the formation of audience numbers. Cinema theaters not only function as technical infrastructure for film screenings but also play a significant role in shaping the culture of film viewing among audiences. Therefore, the development of cinema theater networks is an important factor in ensuring the stable functioning of the film market and the economic efficiency of the film industry.

The formation of the audience is one of the key social and cultural factors of the film market. Through film screenings, the cinema theater system influences the development of viewers' aesthetic tastes, interests, and overall film culture. At the same time, the audience determines the demand for film products and shapes the directions of development within the film market. Therefore, the interrelationship between cinema theater activities and the audience plays an important role in the sustainable development of the film industry.

The infrastructure of modern cinema theaters is one of the key factors that ensures both the technical quality of film screenings and the cultural environment created for audiences. Today, cinema theaters are equipped with high-quality digital projection systems, multi-channel sound technologies, and comfortable viewing conditions, enabling films to be presented at a high standard. In addition, the integration of cinemas within shopping and entertainment centers increases audience attendance and transforms film viewing into a broader cultural

experience. As a result, modern cinema theaters are becoming not only venues for film screenings but also important cultural infrastructures that contribute to the development of film culture.

Conclusion

In summary, the film market, distribution system, and cinema theater network constitute interconnected and complementary components of the film industry. After a film is produced, its delivery to audiences is carried out through distribution mechanisms and the cinema theater system. The coordination between these systems ensures the effective dissemination of film products, the expansion of the audience, and the stable development of the film market. Therefore, the success of the film industry largely depends on the cooperation and effective functioning of these three factors.

The effective functioning of the film market, distribution system, and cinema theater infrastructure plays an important role in the development of national cinema. Through these systems, national film products are delivered to a wide audience, ensuring their cultural and economic impact. At the same time, a well-developed distribution network and cinema theater system contribute to increasing the competitiveness of national cinematography, promoting local films, and expanding film culture. As a result, the improvement of these systems creates a foundation for the sustainable development of the national film industry and its *достоинное* place in the international film arena.

In the future, the development of the film market, distribution, and cinema theater systems will be closely linked with modern technologies, digital platforms, and the expansion of the new media environment. The growth of digital distribution opportunities, online streaming services, and the development of modern cinema infrastructure will further expand the scope of film distribution. At the same time, the effective organization of the film market will contribute to increasing the production of national films and expanding the audience. Consequently, improving the film market, distribution, and cinema theater systems will create an important basis for the sustainable and competitive development of the film industry in the future.

References:

1. D.Bordwell, K.Thompson. Film Art: An Introduction. – New York.: McGraw-Hill. 2019. P-546
2. J.Caldwell. Production Culture: Industrial Reflexivity and Critical Practice in Film and Television. – London.:Duke University Press,2008.P-448.
3. H.Vogel. Entertainment Industry Economics: A Guide for Financial Analysis.– Cambridge University Press, 2020. P-671.

4. De Vany. Hollywood Economics: How Extreme Uncertainty Shapes the Film Industry. – Routledge, 2004. P-332.
5. Litman, B. R. The Motion Picture Mega-Industry.– Allyn & Bacon, 1998. P-340.

